

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION INTO THE ELASTIC IMPACT RESPONSE OF CARBON-FIBRE EPOXY PLATES VALIDATED WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA

T. Franz, V. Balden, and G.N. Nurick

Centre for Research in Computational and Applied Mechanics (CERECAM)

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Cape Town

Rondebosch, 7701, South Africa

SUMMARY: The paper presents a numerical investigation into the mechanical behaviour of fibre-reinforced composite plates subjected to impact loadings. The Finite Element (FE) method is used to predict the elastic response of CFRP plates due to impact below the damage threshold. Of particular interest is the behaviour of CFRP plates with structural discontinuities. The modelling simulates experimental work. The investigations utilise the commercial FE code ABAQUS. All FE models are based on continuum elements. The analysis is performed using ABAQUS Standard with implicit element formulation and ABAQUS Explicit with explicit element formulation. The numerical results obtained using ABAQUS Standard show good agreement with the photoelastic results regarding the formation of the waves. The results obtained using the explicit element formulation indicate that ABAQUS Explicit is better able to predict high velocity phenomena, however, the prediction of the wave formation differs considerably from the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: CFRP, Plate, Impact, Finite Element Analysis

NOMENCLATURE

E	Young's modulus	θ	Fibre direction
G	Shear modulus	ρ	Material density
ϵ_1	Maximum principal in-plane strain		
ϵ_2	Minimum principal in-plane strain	<u>Subscripts:</u>	
φ	Fibre volume fraction	f	Fibre
ν	Poisson's ratio	m	Matrix

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites are under the threat of impact events in a wide range of applications. The anisotropic material properties in conjunction with the transient type of loading cause a complex mechanical response. In addition, composite components are often modified by structural elements, such as openings or stiffeners, which are mechanically critical. The stress-conforming design of composite components which have to sustain impacts, therefore, requires the knowledge of the immediate mechanical response and in particular the influence of the structural elements. The elastic response of CFRP plates due to an impact loading was experimentally investigated by means of the photoelastic stress coating technique [1, 2]. The experimental results are a starting point for the development of a numerical model to predict the behaviour of fibre-reinforced polymer matrix composites upon impact. The numerical models utilise the Finite Element method.

2. SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

The composite material investigated is an unidirectional (UD) 6-ply laminate of Tenax HTA carbon fibres and a LY556-HY917 epoxy matrix with a laminate thickness of 1.5mm. The elastic properties E_1 , E_2 , $E_{\theta=45^\circ}$, and ν_{12} of the unidirectional laminate under impact conditions

are determined in impact tests on bar specimens by means of strain gauges. Using these experimental results and employing relations of anisotropic elasticity and laminate theory, the in-plane elastic properties of the laminate are obtained as follows; $E_1 = 131.3\text{GPa}$, $E_2 = 10.6\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.31$, $\nu_{21} = 0.025$, $G_{12} = 6.03\text{GPa}$. The fibre volume fraction is specified from the laminate manufacturer to be $\phi = 0.6$ [3]. The material density is determined experimentally to be $\rho = 1570\text{kg/m}^3$.

Various plate specimens of the dimensions 310mm by 310mm are made from the laminate; unmodified plates with fibre directions of $\theta = 0^\circ$, 45° , and 90° ; plates with a CFRP T-beam stiffener bonded to one plate surface in different orientations. The stiffener laminate is a 6-ply stitched $\pm 45^\circ$ Tenax HTA carbon fibre laying with LY556-HY917 epoxy matrix. The stiffener laminate has a thickness of 3mm and a fibre volume fraction of $\phi = 0.6$. Since the fibre material, matrix resin, and fibre volume fraction are the same for the plate laminate and the stiffener laminate, the elastic properties determined for the UD plate laminate are applied to the individual UD stiffener laminae. The CFRP plates are single-sided coated with a 3mm thick polycarbonate layer for photoelastic stress analysis purposes. The concentric polycarbonate layer has the dimensions of 260mm by 260mm. The elastic properties of the polycarbonate are $E = 2.45\text{GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.38$ which have been shown to be rate insensitive [4]. The material density is $\rho = 1180\text{kg/m}^3$.

The experimental work, reported in detail in references [1, 2], is conducted using a pneumatic impact test device and an optical set-up distinguished by ultra-short-term flashlights. The photoelastic stress coating technique is employed as it offers the appropriate means for a large-area visualisation of the wave propagation, and is applicable to arbitrary fibre-reinforced polymer-matrix composites. The experimental results give a comprehensive insight into the immediate elastic response of the unmodified plates and plates with local increases and decreases in stiffness upon the impact loadings. The results refer to the influence of; fibre direction, plate boundary conditions, and existence and orientation of structural discontinuities on the wave propagation. The results of stiffened specimens indicate local strain concentrations in stiffener vicinity and areas of attenuated wave propagation. In the areas of attenuated wave propagation lower strain magnitudes are observed compared to plate areas with uninhibited wave propagation.

3. NUMERICAL MODELLING

The commercial finite element code ABAQUS [5] is employed for the numerical analysis. Three-dimensional finite element models of the various plate types as described in the previous section are generated using continuum brick elements. The effective target area of the CFRP plates, excluding the clamped plate edges, is used in the numerical model. This results in dimension of the CFRP plate models of 290mm by 310mm with a thickness of 1.5mm. The dimensions of most of the elements in the plate plane (denoted as 'in-plane' hereinafter) throughout all models, unless otherwise stated, is 5mm by 5mm. Both the CFRP plate and the polycarbonate coating are modelled with two layers of elements in the plate thickness direction which results in a element dimension in thickness direction (denoted as 'out-of-plane') of 0.75mm and 1.5mm, respectively. The size of the elements used for the T-beam CFRP stiffener varies between 3mm by 5mm and 5mm by 5mm in-plane and between 3mm and 5mm out-of-plane. The in-plane size of the CFRP plate elements and polycarbonate elements in the stiffener region is adapted to the in-plane size of the stiffener elements in order to ensure the consistency of the complete model.

For five out of six analyses using ABAQUS Standard (implicit element formulation), the model utilises 20-node quadratic brick elements with reduced integration (C3D20R). The 6-ply plate laminate is modelled by assigning three unidirectional layers through the thickness direction of both layers of elements. The 6-ply $\pm 45^\circ$ -laminate of the stiffener is modelled as

12 unidirectional layer with alternating fibre directions of +45° and -45°. Quadratic FE model are generated for; unmodified plates with the fibre direction $\theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ,$ and 90° ; plates with the fibre direction of $\theta = 0^\circ$ and one stiffener orientated in fibre direction and under 45° to the fibre direction, respectively.

The analysis employing ABAQUS Explicit with explicit element formulation requires a modified model since the element library and material options are restricted compared to ABAQUS Standard. Since 20-noded brick elements are not included in the ABAQUS Explicit element library, 8-node linear brick elements with reduced integration (C3D8R) are used. Additionally, ABAQUS Explicit does not support a composite option for continuum elements. This means that multiple layers cannot be assigned in a continuum element. Hence multidirectional laminates need to be modelled with a separate layer of elements for each ply. In the case of a unidirectional laminate, as used for the CFRP plates in the current studies, several plies can be represented by a single element layer in order to reduce the computational expense. Due to these restrictions, the analysis using ABAQUS Explicit is performed only on a model of one unmodified plate, with the fibre direction of $\theta = 0^\circ$, and the results are compared with those of an analysis of the same plate performed with ABAQUS Standard. The plate model for ABAQUS Standard utilises the same element type C3D8R. However, a difference in the models exists due to different material definitions; a continuous orthotropic material in ABAQUS Explicit versus a layered orthotropic composite in ABAQUS Standard.

Modelling an orthotropic material three-dimensionally requires the specification of the elastic lamina properties in all three dimensions, i.e. $E_1, E_2, E_3, \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}, G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23}$. Since only the in-plane properties are obtained experimentally (see section 2), the transverse properties $E_3, \nu_{13}, G_{13},$ and G_{23} need to be determined. The unidirectional laminate is assumed to exhibit transverse isotropic behaviour. Hence, it is assumed that $E_3 = E_2, \nu_{13} = \nu_{12},$ and $G_{13} = G_{12}$ [6]. The Poisson's ratio ν_{23} is calculated using

$$\nu_{23} = \nu_{f,12}\phi + \nu_m(1-\phi) \left(\frac{1 + \nu_m - \nu_{12}(1-\phi) \frac{E_m}{E_1}}{1 + \nu_m^2 - \nu_m \nu_{12}(1-\phi) \frac{E_m}{E_1}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The shear modulus G_{23} is calculated using [6]

$$G_{23} = \frac{E_2}{2(1 + \nu_{23})} \quad (2)$$

Considering the Poisson's ratio of the Tenax HTA fibre being $\nu_{f,12} = 0.262$ and Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the LY556/HY917 resin being $E_m = 3.3\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_m = 0.35$, the transverse lamina properties are; $E_3 = 10.6\text{GPa}, \nu_{13} = 0.31, \nu_{23} = 0.357, G_{13} = 6.03\text{GPa}, G_{23} = 3.91\text{GPa}$.

The experimental plate boundary conditions, i.e. clamping of two opposite plate edges, are modelled by encastreing the nodes of the appropriate boundaries. The experimental impact loading, applied normal to the laminate plane over a circular area of 13mm diameter at the plate centre, is modelled as a time varying concentrated load with a profile of an unsymmetric triangular form over a period of approximately 30 μs . The force history data, recorded during the experiments by means of a quartz force sensor, is applied to the nodes representing the loading area. The experimental impact loading is imparted to the specimen by a steel anvil which houses the quartz force ring. The anvil is in contact to the specimen before imparting the impact load, and restricts the plate displacement opposite to the impact direction. To represent this displacement constraint, the anvil is included in the numerical models as a rigid surface.

4. RESULTS

The propagation of elastic waves and the deformation of the plate upon impact is shown for some of the plate types investigated in Figure 1 to Figure 4. Each of these figures is structured in the same way. Photoelastic images are given in the top row. The photoelastic images were taken during the experiments at the specified times after the impact. The patterns of isochromatic fringes represent the difference in the principal in-plane strains, $\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2$, at the midplane of the polycarbonate coating. (The difference in the principal in-plane strains, $\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2$, is denoted as 'strain difference' hereinafter.) Contour plots generated from the FE models are shown in the middle row. Like the photoelastic images, the contour plots represent the difference in the principal in-plane strains at the midplane of the polycarbonate. Plots of the deformed shape of the plate are given in the bottom row. The deformed shape plots show the out-of-plane displacement in the entire specimens consisting of the CFRP plate (grey) and the polycarbonate coating (green). The top and bottom plate boundaries are the fixed boundaries. The photoelastic images and the contour plots, however, show only the polycarbonate coating. The impact load is applied and modelled, respectively, at the centre of the rear plate surface, which agrees with the midpoint of the photoelastic images and the contour plots. It should be noted that the times of the contour plots vary to a certain extent from those of the photoelastic images due to restrictions in the numerical analysis. All numerical results presented in Figure 1 to Figure 4 are obtained using ABAQUS Standard.

The photoelastic images of Figure 1 show the wave propagation in an unmodified plate with the fibre direction $\theta = 0^\circ$ from $53\mu\text{s}$ to $201\mu\text{s}$ after the impact. In each image the elliptical shape of the waves caused by the material orthotropy of the unidirectional composite is clearly visible. The principal axes of the wave ellipses coincide with the orthotropic axes of the laminate. The major ellipse axis is orientated in direction of the orthotropic axis x_1 with the major Young's modulus (in fibre direction), and the minor ellipse axis agrees with the orthotropic axis x_2 with the minor Young's modulus (perpendicular to the fibre direction), see photoelastic image at $53\mu\text{s}$. Waves reflected at the top and bottom plate boundary travelling towards the plate centre appear in the images at $153\mu\text{s}$ and $201\mu\text{s}$ after the impact. In the isochromatic fringe patterns, black colour represents the minimum magnitude of the difference in principal in-plane strains (i.e. $\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2 = 0$) while a sequence blue-yellow-red represents an increasing magnitude of the strain difference.

The FE model contour plots in Figure 1 (middle row) compare well with the photoelastic images. The elliptic shape and the orientation of the waves closely match the experimental results. In the contour plots, a light blue seen in the major part of the plot at $55\mu\text{s}$ represents the strain difference being zero. The colour sequence green-yellow-red represents an increasing strain difference magnitude. The fastest waves appearing in the photoelastic images with a very low strain difference magnitude are, however, not represented in the numerical contour plots. The contour plots also do not show any reflected waves which are of a similar low strain difference magnitude as the fastest waves. In the contour plots, the wave zone of maximum strain difference magnitude (depicted by red colour) propagates faster towards the plate boundaries than it is observed in the photoelastic images. The photoelastic patterns indicate the highest strain difference magnitude along the x_1 -axis relative to the impact point and a slightly lower magnitude along the x_2 -axis relative to the impact point while the wave zone of the maximum strain difference magnitude is formed as a closed ellipse in the contour plots. However, a similar trend to a higher strain difference magnitude along the x_1 -axis and a slightly lower value along the x_2 -axis in the same wave ellipse can be seen in the contour plots at wave ellipses of an intermediate strain difference magnitude represented by yellow colour. These wave ellipses are observed in particular in the contour plots at $160\mu\text{s}$ and $204\mu\text{s}$ where orange-red spots along the x_1 -axis indicate the higher strain difference magnitude.

The deformed shape plots (Figure 1 bottom row) show the out-of-plane displacement in the thickness direction of the plate upon impact. The displacement is depicted with a magnification factor of 30 (this magnification factor applies to all deformed shape plots in this paper). The plots represent the deformation of the plate at the same times as the numerical contour plots. The deformed plots agree well with the numerical contour plots and the photoelastic images in terms of the ellipticity and the orientation of the waves and deformation, respectively.

Fibre direction: ||||

Figure 1. Photoelastic images (top), contour plots (middle), and deformed shape plots (bottom) showing the wave propagation in an unmodified plate with $\theta = 0^\circ$

Figure 2 illustrates the wave propagation and the deformation of a plate with the fibre direction of $\theta = 45^\circ$. The orientation of the wave ellipses is governed by the fibre direction and the principal ellipse axes coincide with the orthotropic materials axes x_1 and x_2 . The photoelastic images at $151\mu\text{s}$ and $201\mu\text{s}$ after the impact show wave reflections both at the top and bottom plate boundary, as in the plate with a fibre direction of $\theta = 0^\circ$ (see Figure 1), but also at the free left and right plate boundary. As observed from the plate with $\theta = 0^\circ$, the contour plots and the deformed shape plots of the plate with $\theta = 45^\circ$ do not represent waves of low strain difference magnitude, i.e. fastest waves and reflected waves, which are visible in the photoelastic images.

Fibre direction:

Figure 2. Photoelastic images (top), contour plots (middle), and deformed shape plots (bottom) showing the wave propagation in an unmodified plate with $\theta = 45^\circ$

The wave propagation in a plate with a stiffener is shown in Figure 3. The fibre direction of the CFRP plate is $\theta = 0^\circ$. The stiffener bonded to the rear surface of the CFRP plate is orientated in fibre direction. The position of the stiffener is marked in the photoelastic image at $101\mu\text{s}$. It is observed in the photoelastic images, the contour plots, and the deformed shape plots of Figure 3 that the stiffener affects the wave propagation and the deformation only locally. The effects of the stiffener are negligible in the left part of the plate where the shape and orientation of the waves as well as the deformation coincide with those of the unmodified plate of the same fibre direction, see Figure 1. In the photoelastic images, effects of the stiffener in the right part of the specimen are observed as follows; strain concentrations between the impact point and the stiffener; a strain concentration at the stiffener flange edge, and the attenuation of the wave propagation. The attenuation of the wave propagation and the accompanying reduction of the out-of-plane displacement are represented in the contour plots and the deformed shape plots. The strain concentrations, i.e. areas of an increased strain difference magnitude are, however, different in the contour plots and the photoelastic images. The strain concentrations are situated further towards the plate boundaries. This is expected to be due to the fact that the predicted propagation of the wave zone of the maximum strain difference magnitude exceeds the experimental result (as described for the unmodified plate shown in Figure 1). The strain concentration along the x_2 -axis is not represented in the contour plots.

Fibre direction: ||||

Figure 3. Photoelastic images (top), contour plots (middle), and deformed shape plots (bottom) showing the wave propagation in a plate with a 0°-stiffener

Figure 4 shows the photoelastic and numerical results for a plate with a stiffener orientated at 45° to the fibre direction of $\theta = 0^\circ$. The stiffener orientation is the only difference to the plate shown in Figure 3. The effects of the stiffener are observed to be similar to the plate with the 0°-stiffener. The localised strain concentrations in the area between the stiffener and the impact point can be recognised in the photoelastic images. As in Figure 3, the numerical contour plots predict the strain concentrations further away from the impact point. The attenuation of the wave propagation and the accompanying reduction of the out-of-plane displacement is indicated in the lower left-hand corner of the plate in the photoelastic images and the numerical plots.

Fibre direction: ||||

Figure 4. Photoelastic images (top), contour plots (middle), and deformed shape plots (bottom) showing the wave propagation in a plate with a 45°-stiffener

Figure 5 shows three series of contour plots and one series of deformed shape plots of the out-of-plane displacement of an unmodified plate with the fibre direction of $\theta = 0^\circ$. Three different analyses are conducted to evaluate the capabilities of ABAQUS Explicit incorporating explicit element formulation with regard to the elastic response of composites upon impact loadings;

- implicit element formulation analysis of a FE model utilising quadratic brick elements (C3D20R) shown in the 1st row of Figure 5
- implicit element formulation analysis of a FE model utilising linear brick elements (C3D8R) shown in the 2nd row of Figure 5
- explicit element formulation analysis of a FE model utilising linear brick elements (C3D8R) shown in the 3rd and 4th row of Figure 5

The slightly differing times of the analyses with different element formulation are due to different algorithms for the calculation of the increment time in ABAQUS Standard and ABAQUS Explicit. The contour plots of the quadratic FE model and the linear FE model analysed with implicit element formulation compare reasonably. The differences may be attributed to the different element types.

Fibre direction: ||||

Figure 5. Numerical plots showing the transverse displacement due to wave propagation in a plate with $\theta = 0^\circ$; model with quadratic elements C3D20R and implicit element formulation (1st row), model with linear elements C3D8R and implicit element formulation (2nd row), model with linear elements C3D8R and explicit element formulation (3rd and 4th row)

The contour plots of the linear FE model analysed with explicit element formulation, however, differ considerably from the implicit element formulation results. While the displacement field at the plate centre is elliptically shaped in all three models, the explicit element formulation results in a more square shaped displacement field towards the plate boundaries which is associated with fast propagating waves. This particular shape of the displacement field is also represented in the deformed shape plots of the linear model analysed with explicit

element formulation (see 4th row of Figure 5). The deformed shape plots additionally show that the explicit element formulation in ABAQUS Explicit, tailored for modelling transient dynamic events such as impact and blast, is able to predict wave reflections. Reflected waves are observed in the deformed shape plots at 154 μ s and 204 μ s propagating from the top and bottom plate boundary towards the plate centre.

5. DISCUSSION

The numerical results obtained by FE analysis with implicit element formulation agree well with the photoelastic fringe patterns regarding the formation of the elastic waves upon impact for all plates investigated. The predicted ellipticity of the waves, the orientation of the wave ellipses governed by the fibre direction of the unidirectional CFRP laminate, and the wave attenuation by the stiffener matches the experimental results closely (Figure 1 to Figure 4).

The wave formation predicted by the numerical analysis performed with explicit element formulation differs considerably from the implicit element formulation results and, hence, from the experimental results, see Figure 5. Reasons for the difference have not yet been concluded. ABAQUS Explicit does not provide the option to model layered composites using continuum elements. Thus, the ABAQUS Explicit model differs from the ABAQUS Standard models such that the composite definition is not included. It has to be investigated whether the difference in the composite definition results in the different predictions although the anisotropic elastic properties of the composite material are specified in the same way.

The fastest waves and reflected waves, both of a small magnitude, represented in the photoelastic images are not observed in the numerical plots obtained using ABAQUS Standard (Figure 1 to Figure 4). The deformed shape plots of the ABAQUS Explicit results, however, predict wave reflections (Figure 5). It is assumed that ABAQUS Explicit is more capable to predict high velocity events than ABAQUS Standard irrespective the difference in the wave form of the prediction and experiments.

The contour plots, obtained using ABAQUS Standard, predict that the wave causing maximum magnitude of the strain difference propagates faster towards the plate boundaries than is observed in the photoelastic images (Figure 1 to Figure 4). Additionally, the difference in the strain difference magnitude along the orthotropic axes x_1 and x_2 is less distinctive in the numerical results than in the experimental results. Currently, material damping is not included in the numerical models. ABAQUS offers different material damping options as built-in features (mass damping and stiffness damping) which, however, do not allow the definition of anisotropic damping properties as required for composite materials. Since damping is assumed to effect the wave propagation, different results regarding the propagation of the wave causing the maximum strain difference magnitude are expected when material damping is included in the model. The difference in the strain difference magnitude along the orthotropic axes might also be affected as the damping coefficients of the UD CFRP laminate are different in the fibre direction and perpendicular to the fibre direction.

Due to limitations of the user subroutine library of ABAQUS Explicit, the difference in principal in-plane strains is not yet readily available. Observations regarding the strain difference contour plots can not be conducted and the comparison is limited to deformed shape plots.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The prediction of the formation of elastic waves in CFRP plates upon impact loading by means of Finite Element analysis using ABAQUS has been shown to agree well with experimental results. Certain topics need to be addressed in more detail; the prediction of elastic waves of low magnitude, incorporating anisotropic material damping, and modelling of layered composites in ABAQUS Explicit. The described work is currently ongoing.

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